

Coordination of Al(III), Be(II) and Cu(II) Ions with 1,7-Dihydroxy-4-sulfo-2-naphthoic and 3,5-Dihydroxy-7-sulfo-2-naphthoic Acids in Aqueous Sodium Perchlorate Medium

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The aluminium(III), beryllium(II) and copper(II) complex formation of sodium 1,7-dihydroxy-4-sulfonato-2-naphthoic and sodium 3,5-dihydroxy-7-sulfonato-2-naphthoic acids, $\text{Na}^+\text{H}_2\text{L}^-$, has been studied in aqueous solution at ionic strength 0.5 (NaClO_4 as main electrolyte) and $25.0 \pm 0.1^\circ$ by means of potentiometric pH titrations. The protonation of the ligand anions has been investigated by standard spectrophotometric and potentiometric methods under the same conditions.

In the metal-ligand equilibrium systems, the experimental data can be explained with the formation of the complexes MHL^- , ML_2^{2-} , $\text{MH}_2\text{L}_2^{4-}$, MHL_2^{2-} and ML_2^{4-} ($\text{M} = \text{Cu}$ or Be), and AlHL , AlL^- , AlHL_2^{4-} , AlL_2^{5-} and AlL_3^{6-} when an excess of the ligand is present and $\text{pH} < 9$. Polynuclear complex compounds were not found in detectable amounts in potentiometric titrations. However, this might be only due to the experimental conditions, since accurate potential readings were available only with an excess of the ligand in the solutions to be titrated.

PPOTENTIOMETRIC and spectrophotometric studies on the complexes formed between beryllium(II), copper(II) and aluminium(III) and a number of aromatic sulfo-substituted *o*-hydroxy-carboxylic acids have been reported in our previous papers¹⁻⁷. All the previous ligands have been mono- or disulfonic acid derivatives of salicylic, 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic or 3-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acids, thus containing one hydroxyl group and one carboxyl group in *ortho*-positions to each other, and one or two sulfonato groups. 1,7-Dihydroxy-4-sulfo-2-naphthoic and 3,5-dihydroxy-7-sulfo-2-naphthoic acids are new reagents for investigation of metal complex formation and the number of hydroxyl groups is the main difference between these and the compounds studied earlier. The present investigation was undertaken to determine the composition and stability of the species formed in the equilibrium system: H^+ -ligand, Be^{2+} -ligand, Cu^{2+} -ligand and Al^{3+} -ligand (where ligand is either 1,7-dihydroxy-4-sulfonato-2-naphthoic acid or 3,5-dihydroxy-7-sulfonato-2-naphthoic acid anion). A comparison of the results obtained with 1-hydroxy-4-sulfo-2-naphthoic, 1-hydroxy-7-sulfo-2-naphthoic, 1-hydroxy-4,7-disulfo-2-naphthoic, 3-hydroxy-4-sulfo-2-naphthoic, 3-hydroxy-5-sulfo-2-naphthoic, 3-hydroxy-7-sulfo-2-naphthoic and 3-hydroxy-5,7-disulfo-2-naphthoic acids permits a discussion of the effects of the "lone" hydroxyl group (the hydroxyl group without neighbouring substituents) on the protonation and metal complex formation of the salicylic-type ligands of the naphthalene series. The stability constants of Be^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Al^{3+} com-

plexes with 1,7-dihydroxy-4-sulfo-2-naphthoic acid have been reported in an earlier paper⁸.

The experimental methods used in this investigation were the same as described in the earlier studies, i.e. standard potentiometric and spectrophotometric methods. All experiments were performed in a medium of ionic strength 0.5 M, with sodium perchlorate as the neutral salt. The temperature was $25.0 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Notations :

1,7-Dihydroxy-4-sulfonato-2-naphthoic acid and 3,5-dihydroxy-7-sulfonato-2-naphthoic acid anions, $[\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_4\text{SO}_3(\text{OH})_2\text{COOH}]^-$, are written as H_2L^- . C_M , C_H and C_L denote the total concentrations of metal, free and dissociable hydrogen ions, and ligand anion, respectively. $[\text{M}]$, $[\text{H}^+]$ and $[\text{L}]$ denote the concentrations of free metal ion, hydrogen ion and ligand anion respectively.

$\beta_{q,p,r}$ is the overall stability constant for the complex $\text{M}_q\text{H}_p\text{L}_r$, defined as

$$\beta_{q,p,r} = [\text{M}_q\text{H}_p\text{L}_r] / [\text{M}]^q [\text{H}]^p [\text{L}]^r \quad \dots (1)$$

where $q \geq 0$, $p \geq 0$, $r \geq 0$, and $q + p + r \geq 2$.

$$\bar{n}_H = (C_H - [\text{H}^+] + [\text{OH}^-]) / C_L \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\bar{n} = (C_L - \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} [\text{H}_j\text{L}]) / C_M \quad \dots (3)$$

$\bar{n}_H$ = the mean number of hydrogen ions bound per ligand anion, and

$\bar{n}$ = the mean number of ligand anions bound per metal ion.

Experimental

Reagents: Sodium 1,7-dihydroxy-4-sulfonato-2-naphthoic and sodium 3,5-dihydroxy-7-sulfonato-2-naphthoic acids were prepared on alkali fusion from 1-hydroxy-4,7-disulfo-2-naphthoic acid and 3-hydroxy-5,7-disulfo-2-naphthoic acid, respectively. The purity of the compounds was checked by ^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectrometry.

Potentiometric measurements: The emf (E) of a galvanic cell of the following type was measured:

The system was calibrated before each titration by measuring the emf (E_R) when the titration vessel contained a solution of known free hydrogen ion concentration, $[\text{H}^+]_R$. The unknown hydrogen ion concentration, $[\text{H}^+]$, was then calculated from the equation:

$$-2.303 \text{ RT/F} \log \left(\frac{[\text{H}^+]}{[\text{H}^+]_R} \right) = (E_R - E_j) - (E - E_j') \quad (4)$$

where $R=8.314 \text{ JK}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}$, $T=298.15 \text{ K}$ and $F=96487 \text{ C mol}^{-1}$. E_j and E_j' are the liquid junction potentials. The liquid junction potentials depend mainly on the free hydrogen ion concentration in the solutions, and E_j is then a linear function of $[\text{H}^+]$, $E_j([\text{H}^+])=j([\text{H}^+])$, where j is a constant.

The potentiometric measurements were carried out with a Radiometer digital titration system DTS 633, consisting of an autoburette ABU 13 or 80, a pH meter, PHM 64, and a digital titrator, TTT 61, with an equal increment accessory constructed in this laboratory.

The protonation constants of the ligand anions were determined in solutions without any metal present. In these measurements C_L was kept constant and C_H was varied by adding NaOH or HClO_4 to the solution with different $C_L : C_H$ ratios. The experimental data for evaluating the protonation constants consist of seven different emf titrations for each ligand acid, where C_L and $-\log [\text{H}^+]$ varied between 0.001 and 0.03 M, and 2.3 and 12, respectively.

The stabilities of the beryllium(II), aluminium(III) and copper(II) complexes of 1,7-dihydroxy-4-sulfo-2-naphthoic and 3,5-dihydroxy-7-sulfo-2-naphthoic acids were determined by measuring the emf values in galvanic cells of the kind described above. During the titrations the ratio $C_L : C_M$ was kept constant and C_H was varied by adding NaOH. The concentrations C_M and C_L in the starting solutions and the $-\log [\text{H}^+]$ ranges for the Be^{2+} , Al^{3+} and Cu^{2+} systems with 3,5-dihydroxy-7-sulfo-2-naphthoic acid are given in Table 1.

Spectrophotometric measurements: A Pye Unicam SP 8-100 UV-vis spectrophotometer, equipped with a 10 mm autocell and a superimpose accessory was used for the purpose. The absorbance readings were taken in the wavelength range 300-

TABLE 1—NUMBER OF POTENTIAL READINGS, INITIAL CONCENTRATIONS, C_M AND C_L , AND THE $-\log [\text{H}^+]$ RANGES FOR THE TITRATIONS CARRIED OUT FOR EVALUATING THE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE BERYLLIUM(II), ALUMINIUM(III) AND COPPER(II) 3,5-DIHYDROXY-7-SULFONATO-2-NAPHTHOIC ACID COMPLEXES

Expt.	No. of readings	Metal	C_M/M	C_L/M	$\log [\text{H}^+]$ range
1	47	Be	0.00096	0.00115	3.21-9.49
2	55	"	0.00096	0.00323	3.20-8.26
3	54	"	0.00096	0.00545	3.20-8.06
4	38	"	0.00192	0.00323	3.16-6.34
5	44	"	0.00192	0.00538	3.11-7.79
6	34	"	0.00384	0.00539	3.07-6.09
7	58	"	0.00384	0.02150	3.09-8.21
8	36	Al	0.00097	0.00330	3.10-6.03
9	44	"	0.00097	0.00550	3.10-8.42
10	57	"	0.00097	0.00770	3.13-8.13
11	47	"	0.00194	0.00704	3.07-8.07
12	53	"	0.00194	0.01408	3.07-8.21
13	58	"	0.00194	0.02816	3.04-8.11
14	57	"	0.00388	0.02820	3.00-8.07
15	33	Cu	0.00099	0.00218	3.38-9.98
16	41	"	0.00099	0.00327	3.40-9.08
17	45	"	0.00099	0.00545	3.44-8.25
18	51	"	0.00149	0.00545	3.41-8.15
19	55	"	0.00200	0.00545	3.36-8.91
20	53	"	0.00399	0.01090	3.32-8.75
21	55	"	0.00399	0.02180	3.00-8.80

420 nm with an interval of 5 nm. C_L was varied in these measurements between 0.00005 and 0.0003 M. In evaluating the protonation constants of the ligand anion, altogether 36 test solutions were prepared with varying pH values ($2 < -\log [\text{H}^+] < 13.5$) for each H^+ -ligand system.

Calculations: The equilibrium constants were calculated as overall stability constants (Equation 1) with the programme SCOGS¹⁰ from the potentiometric data and with the programme SQUAD¹¹ from the spectrophotometric (absorbance-pH) data on a Univac 1100/20 computer.

Results and Discussion

The proton-ligand systems: The search of the potentiometric data was initiated by drawing the

Fig. 1. Experimental (points) and calculated (solid line) $\bar{n}_H$ values vs $-\log [\text{H}^+]$ for 3,5-dihydroxy-7-sulfo-2-naphthoic acid at $I=0.5$ (NaClO_4) and $t=25^\circ$.

$\bar{n}_H$ vs $(-\log [H^+])$ plots for both H_2L^+ -ligand systems (Fig. 1). It can be seen from the figure that the $\bar{n}_H$ $(-\log [H^+])$ function is independent of C_L , which would indicate that only a series of monomeric H_iL species is formed. These plots further suggest that these species are H_2L^+ , H_2L^{2+} , HL^{3+} and L^{4+} , because the $\bar{n}_H$ values are all between 2.4 and 0.9 and 2.8 and 0.7, respectively, for 1,7-dihydroxy-4-

sulfo-2-naphthoic acid and 3,5-dihydroxy-7-sulfo-2-naphthoic acid. A least-squares refinement of the potentiometric data gave the values of the protonation constants as shown in Table 2.

Fig. 2 and 3 show the uv-vis absorption spectra of 1,7-dihydroxy-4-sulfo-2-naphthoic and 3,5-dihydroxy-7-sulfo-2-naphthoic acids at various pH values

TABLE 2—THE PROTONATION CONSTANTS OF 3,5-DIHYDROXY-7-SULFO-2-NAPHTHOIC (1) AND 1,7-DIHYDROXY-4-SULFO-2-NAPHTHOIC (2) ACIDS AT $I=0.5$ ($NaClO_4$) AND 25° . THE QUOTED ERRORS ARE THREE TIMES THE STANDARD DEVIATIONS $k_{0.2,1} = K(HL^{2+} + H^+ = H_2L^{2+})$ AND $k_{0.3,1} = K(H_2L^{2+} + H^+ = H_3L^{3+})$, gl = POTENTIOMETRIC METHOD AND sp = SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHOD

Ligand/ method	$\log \beta_{0.1,1}$	$\log \beta_{0.2,1}$	$\log \beta_{0.3,1}$	$\log k_{0.2,1}$	$\log k_{0.3,1}$	Refs.
(1)/ <i>gl</i>	12.355 ± 0.015	20.809 ± 0.018	23.314 ± 0.003	8.45	2.50	This work
(1)/ <i>sp</i>	12.374 ± 0.021	20.745 ± 0.024	23.268 ± 0.012	8.37	2.52	8
(2)/ <i>gl</i>	11.93 ± 0.10	20.806 ± 0.010	23.469 ± 0.007	8.88	2.66	8
(2)/ <i>sp</i>	12.254 ± 0.050	21.064 ± 0.010	23.748 ± 0.006	8.81	2.68	8

Fig. 2. UV-vis absorption spectra of 1,7-dihydroxy-4-sulfo-2-naphthoic acid at various pH values between 2 and 13 ($C_L = 0.0002 M$) at $I=0.5$ ($NaClO_4$) and $t = 25^\circ$.

between 2 and 13. As can be seen, there are three distinct pH regions displaying different patterns of change in the absorption spectra of the ligand acids: (1) about $2 < pH < 5$, (2) $5 < pH < 10$ and $pH > 10$. In both systems isosbestic points appear at different pH regions, which also suggest that three different protonation reactions take place in the pH range studied. Spectral data for the ligand anions studied are compiled in Table 3, and the protonation constants, obtained spectrophotometrically in Table 2.

Comparison of the protonation constants obtained potentiometrically and spectrophotometrically shows that the values of each constant for 3,5-dihydroxy-7-sulfo-2-naphthoic acid and the values of the second and third protonation constants for 1,7-dihydroxy-4-sulfo-2-naphthoic acid are in fair agreement with each other, whereas the $\log \beta_{0.1,1}$ value for 1,7-dihydroxy-4-sulfo-2-naphthoic acid evaluated potentiometrically is about 0.3 log units lower than that determined spectrophotometrically. Because the first protonation reaction takes place in very alkaline solutions, the spectrophotometric method (when buffer solutions are used) is more reliable than the potentiometric method

Fig. 3. UV-vis absorption spectra of 3,5-dihydroxy-7-sulfo-2-naphthoic acid at various pH values between 1 and 13.2 (A and B: $C_L = 0.000226 M$ and C: $C_L = 0.000113 M$) at $I=0.5$ ($NaClO_4$) and $t = 25^\circ$.

TABLE 3—THE SPECTRAL DATA FOR 1,7-DIHYDROXY-4-SULFO-2-NAPHTHOIC AND 3,5-DIHYDROXY-7-SULFO-2-NAPHTHOIC ACIDS IN AN AQUEOUS SOLUTION AT 25°

Species	λ_{max}/nm	$\epsilon_{max}/cm^{-1}M^{-1}$	Isosbestic points/nm
1,7-Dihydroxy-4-sulfo-2-naphthoic acid			
H ₂ L ⁻	358.5	3 840	} 358 and 392
H ₃ L ²⁻	336.5	4 000	
HL ⁻	346.5	4 040	} 314 and 354
L ⁻	360.0	3 400	
	359.0	4 000	
3,5-Dihydroxy-7-sulfo-2-naphthoic acid			
H ₂ L ⁻	364.5	1 860	} 360.0
H ₃ L ²⁻	355.0	1 850	
HL ⁻	336.0	3 090	} 309.5
L ⁻	314.0	5 800	
	334.0	5 700	} 381.0

Fig. 4. Part of the experimental data presented as $\bar{n}(-\log [L])$ curves for copper(II)-1,7-dihydroxy-4-sulfo-2-naphthoic acid equilibrium system.

(when the glass electrode is used). Hence the value obtained spectrophotometrically for $\log \beta_{0.1.1}$ for 1,7-dihydroxy-4-sulfo-2-naphthoic acid was used in the calculations of the stability constants of the metal complexes.

The present ligands seem to be weaker as acids with respect to the neighbouring carboxyl and hydroxyl groups than the various mono- and disulfonato derivatives of 1- and 3-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acids studied earlier when the difference between the ionic strengths in the determinations has been taken into account¹⁻⁹. Further, it can be noted that the protonation constants of the hydroxyl groups at carbons C-7 and C-4 are about the same as those of 1- and 2-naphtholsulfonates¹². It is also worth adding that none of the studied sulfonated hydroxycarboxylic acids, including the present dihydroxy derivatives, dimerizes within the available concentration limits.

3,5-Dihydroxy-7-sulfo-2-naphthoic acid is a stronger acid than 1,7-dihydroxy-4-sulfo-2-naphthoic acid with respect to the "lonesome" hydroxyl group as well as the carboxyl group, whereas the acidity of the other hydroxyl group seems to be the reverse.

The metal-ligand systems: The search for the complex species in the different metal-ligand systems was begun as usual by drawing the Bjerrum plots, $\bar{n}=f(-\log[L])$, for each system. As can be seen from Fig 4, $\bar{n}$ is not only a function of $-\log[L]$ for the copper-ligand equilibrium system, but depends

as well on C_L . Thus, the formation of the complexes MH_pL_r ($p \neq 0$) must be taken into consideration. The same observation was made for the other equilibrium systems. The highest experimental $\bar{n}$ values for the beryllium or copper, and aluminium systems were under 2 and 3, respectively, indicating that complexes with at least two ligands per beryllium or copper ion and three ligands per aluminium ion must be formed. Several sets of constants of different MH_pL_r complexes were calculated for each metal-ligand equilibrium system. The reliability of the equilibrium constants obtained in these calculations was checked through comparison of the experimental and calculated $\bar{n}$ values. The best explanations for the potentiometric data were the sets of the complexes MHL^- , ML^{2-} , $MH_2L_2^{4-}$, MHL_2^{2-} and ML_3^{3-} ($M=Be$ or Cu) and $AlHL^-$, $AlHL_2^{4-}$, AlL_2^{3-} and AlL_3^{3-} with the stability constants given in Table 4. It is reasonable to consider that the protons in the "acidic" complexes are those of the hydroxyl group at carbon C-7 or C-4, and that the ML_r species are formed either (a) via the dissociation of these protons or (b) via the direct reduction between metal and L^{4-} anions. Polynuclear complex compounds were not found in detectable amounts in potentiometric titrations. However, this might only be due to the experimental conditions, since accurate potential readings were available only with an excess of the ligand in the solutions to be titrated. Spectrophotometric

TABLE 4—THE STABILITY CONSTANTS FOR THE DIFFERENT METAL-3,5-DIHYDROXY-7-SULFO-2-NAPHTHOIC ACID AND METAL-1,7-DIHYDROXY-4-SULFO-2-NAPHTHOIC ACID EQUILIBRIUM SYSTEMS AT $I=0.5$ ($NaClO_4$) AND 25°

q, p, r	$\log \beta_{AlqH_pL_r}$	$\log \beta_{BeqH_pL_r}$	$\log \beta_{CuqH_pL_r}$	Refs.
Metal-3,5-Dihydroxy-4-sulfo-2-naphthoic acid system				
1,1,1	20.651 ± 0.026	20.004 ± 0.015	17.805 ± 0.018	This work
1,0,1	16.001 ± 0.025	13.64 ± 0.10	10.205 ± 0.025	"
1,2,2	—	37.996 ± 0.036	33.162 ± 0.046	"
1,1,2	32.443 ± 0.042	29.848 ± 0.036	24.60 ± 0.05	"
1,0,2	24.089 ± 0.048	20.789 ± 0.046	15.885 ± 0.036	"
1,0,3	30.849 ± 0.048	—	—	"
Metal-1,7-Dihydroxy-4-sulfo-2-naphthoic acid system				
1,1,1	20.001 ± 0.022	20.327 ± 0.015	18.576 ± 0.030	8
1,0,1	14.952 ± 0.030	14.43 ± 0.05	11.79 ± 0.06	"
1,2,2	—	38.762 ± 0.025	35.56 ± 0.05	"
1,1,2	—	30.11 ± 0.05	27.06 ± 0.05	"
1,0,2	30.80 ± 0.08	20.854 ± 0.030	17.418 ± 0.040	"
1,0,3	22.14 ± 0.09	—	—	"
	28.21 ± 0.08	—	—	"

measurements confirmed the polymerization in acidic metal-ligand solutions where there was a large excess of metal ion with respect to the ligand (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Absorbance plot obtained by the continuous variation method for beryllium(II)-1,7-dihydroxy-4-sulfo-2-naphthoic acid system.

The stability of the present metal complexes follows the general order obtained many times earlier with related chelation agents containing oxygen-oxygen donor atoms, viz, $AlL_n > BeL_n > CuL_n$.

The beryllium and copper 1,7-dihydroxy-4-sulfo-2-naphthoic acid complexes are more stable than the corresponding 3,5-dihydroxy-7-sulfo-2-naphthoic acid complexes. In the case of the aluminium complexes the mutual stability order is reverse.

The present dihydroxy-2-naphthoic acid sulfonates form more stable 1:1 complexes than the different mono- and disulfonato derivatives of 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic and 3-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acids. On the other hand, the addition of a second ligand molecule to the ML complexes is significantly more difficult when the sulfonato group at the carbon C-5 of 3-hydroxy-7-disulfonato-2-naphthoic acid or at carbon C-7 of 1-hydroxy-4,7-disulfonato-2-naphthoic acid is replaced with the hydroxyl group (the $\log k_1/k_2$ values for the 1,7-dihydroxy-7-sulfonato-2-naphthoic acid and 3,5-dihydroxy-7-sulfonato-2-naphthoic acid complexes are about twice those for the 1-hydroxy-4,7-disulfonato-2-naphthoic acid and 3-hydroxy-5,7-disulfonato-2-naphthoic acid complexes).

TABLE 5—THE PROTONATION CONSTANTS OF ML AND ML_2 (CHARGES ARE OMITTED) COMPLEXES OF 3,5-DI-HYDROXY-7-SULFO-2-NAPHTHOIC AND (1) AND 1,7-DIHYDROXY-4-SULFO-2-NAPHTHOIC ACID (2) AT I = 0.5 (NaClO₄) AND 25°. $K_{1.1.1}^H = K(ML + H - MHL)$, $K_{1.1.2}^H = K(ML_2 + H - MHL_2)$ AND $K_{1.2.2}^H = K(MHL_2 + H - MH_2L_2)$

Metal	Ligand	$\log K_{1.1.1}^H$	$\log K_{1.1.2}^H$	$\log K_{1.2.2}^H$	Refs.
Al	(1)	4.65	8.35	8.15	"
Be	"	6.36	9.06	8.56	8
Cu	"	7.60	8.72	—	"
Al	(2)	5.05	8.66	8.65	"
Be	"	5.90	9.26	8.50	"
Cu	"	6.79	9.64	—	"

Table 5 shows the protonation constants of the 1:1 and 1:2 complexes. The following conclusions can be drawn on the basis of these constants: (a) the acidity of the protons in the MH_pL_r complexes increases with the increasing stability of the

Fig. 6. Three-dimensional representation of the formation of the different aluminium species: (A) Al^{3+} , (B) $AlHL$, (C) AlL^- , (D) $AlHL_4^{4-}$, (E) AlL_4^{3-} and (F) AlL_4^{2-} with 1,7-dihydroxy-4-sulfo-2-naphthoic acid,

ML_r complexes, (b) the acidity of the hydroxyl group at carbon C-7 is significantly higher in the 1 : 1 complexes than in the free ligand anion and (c) the protonation constants of the 1 : 2 complexes are, on an average, of the same value as the second protonation constant of the ligand anion.

The aluminium(III), beryllium(II) and copper(II) complex formation of 1,7-dihydroxy-4-sulfo-2-naphthoic and 3,5-dihydroxy-7-sulfo-2-naphthoic acids depend on the free hydrogen ion and ligand anion concentrations if there is an excess of the ligand acid present in the solutions. Thus, all the present equilibrium systems can be displayed as a function of [H⁺] and [L⁴⁻]. Fig. 6 shows the formation of various aluminium species three-dimensionally for 1,7-dihydroxy-4-sulfo-2-naphthoic acid in the pH and -log [L] ranges studied and assuming that there is an excess of the ligand present. For the sake of clarity, the formation of each species is presented in a separate figure.

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